

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OCHIGBO****FIRST NAME: MARIA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5 - 13)
3. Some rules of Thumbs for writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One? (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
5. American vs. British English Basic Differences and Influences of Change (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Sample Corrections to papers (EUCLID 2019, 36 - 43)
7. CMS Crib sheet (EUCLID 2019, 44 – 55)

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D period one, fixated on building the writing skills of doctoral students to capacitate them to plan early, think creatively, answer a question or task, as well as write excellent papers that have minimal grammatical errors, plagiarism and follow stipulated rule of style and citation (EUCLID 2019, 24 - 25). The coursepack contains a mix of right and wrong style of rule, this was intentional as captured under important notice on page Roman numeral ii (EUCLID 2019). The coursepack acts as a guide and, as a test of my knowledge on **essay writing, plagiarism**, referencing, grammar, sentence, paragraph, use of United States (US) versus United Kingdom (UK) English, abbreviations, contents of **Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) Crib Sheet**. The coursepack provides the essential steps, instructions, and examples required to write an essay, that aims to convince readers of an evidence-based idea (EUCLID 2019, 1). Chapters one to seven focused on all essential steps, information required and pitfalls to avoid in writing good essay or paper. It is timely and useful to capacitate and form a solid foundation that will help me to write papers and dissertation that are required in my doctoral studies. In addition to the coursepack, I watched 3 videos; 1-5, use of Zotero and, basic ACA-401D tutorial which provided information with demonstrations on EUCLID's templates, tools and how to navigate the courses. The videos plus the coursepack containing "**sample corrections to paper**" were valuable and helpful to start my exciting doctoral studies journey.

2) MY REACTION TO THE COURSEPACK

a) First point explained

The title of the first chapter of this course pack is “**essay writing**,” I thought the task was easy because I prepare official reports regularly. However, I discovered that writing a response paper using a specific style is difficult. The EUCLID 2019 coursepack and videos made it easier in this bumpy start of my doctoral studies (1). The aim of the first chapter was written to make essay and academic writing easy for students like myself. The headings for the chapter are “essay writing,” and “the basics,” was inserted as second heading; however, the correct title of this chapter is “the basic of essay writing,” authored by University of South Wales, Sydney, Australia (2020). Aside the benefits of this coursepack to my doctoral studies, the chapter provides an excellent framework that will improve my professional and academic writing skills. The content outlined the basic steps required for writing good papers and the need to start early did not help me, so I need to comply with timelines in my essay plan to aid timely completion of the paper. Researching the topic, helped me to find the original article (UNSW 2020,1-2) which assisted me to figure out the errors in this chapter and provided secondary data and information that has answered one of the key questions of this response paper.

I noticed the right and wrong use of textbox; while one was correct, the others have too much information (EUCLID 2019, 3-4). Other errors in chapter one is; the use of two unlinked headings with only one of the heading captured in the table of content, the use of Australian English (like UK English); while other chapter used US or/and UK English (EUCLID 2019, 24, 27). In addition to no bullet added to first sentence “An academic essay should answer a question or task” (EUCLID 2019, 1), improper labeling of third subheading, the information written under the subheading “structure” should be summarized using bullets or inserted in SmartArt figure (EUCLID 2019, 3).

b) Second point explained

The second chapter defines **plagiarism**, provides examples of plagiarism, what, when, why and how to cite, how to avoid **plagiarism**, and the different citing methods that can be used in essay writing. Further explanation showed examples of appropriate and inappropriate quotations and paraphrases. Just as medicines are used as solutions for diseases, proper citation of author and information source is the solution for plagiarism. Chapter two has advanced my knowledge on when and how to use quotations, paraphrase an author’s findings about a topic as well as the use of in-text citation and list of cited works (EUCLID 2019, 6,48). To learn more, I surfed the web and found that Turabian style of referencing uses Footnotes or Endnotes and a Bibliography (Belmont 2020, 1).

The errors in chapter two are: making every point a second heading and wrong use of headings, under “why mention the source,” the first two lines were not bulleted (EUCLID 2019, 5) and the use of bold font and upper case in sentences (EUCLID 2019, 5,8). In the session of paraphrase, it was wrong to label the examples as second subheadings plus

improper formatting of bullets (EUCLID 2019, 8-9). The “in-text citations,” is wrong (EULID 2019, 6). The information under “in-text citation” and “technical communication process and products,” were repeated with the wrong use of upper case. The session on list of work cited was poorly organized with wrong subheadings; for instances “For books use the following format” (EUCLID 2019, 11), it should be written as sub-sub heading 1-for books, sub-subheading 2- online work etc. There are several wrong uses of quotation signs and lack of in-cite reference to accompany the quotations. The information flow under “the list of sited work,” is not connected, I had to read through several times to establish the link. The session on “personal vs academic style” and “Achieving “Logical Flow” (EUCLID 2019, 12, 13) should not be part of this chapter two, it can form be part of chapter one (EUCLID 2019, 1) or chapter eight (EUCLID 2019, 44).

c) Third point explained

Chapter three, titled “**Some rules of Thumbs for writing papers,**” re-echoes some key messages that will help me in **essay writing** and response papers. The new knowledge I have acquired is that my sentence should be less than five lines while the paragraphs in my papers should not be up to twenty lines i.e. anytime I am writing and it does not comply I should look for a way to either summarize my points or break it and then include a connecting sentence between the two paragraphs. As a medical person, I need to remember to keep my writing clear, simple and precise so that non-medical personnel can understand the contents of my medical writeups (EUCLID 2019, 15). The **CMS Crib Sheet** provides more information on the formatting styles for books, papers etc. (EUCLID 2019, 44).

I observed that similar information already shared in chapter one was repeated in this chapter. Under the first part titled, “state the main thesis” (EUCLID 2019, 14) is similar in content with “Establish a possible thesis/ point of view” (EUCLID 2019, 1). While “stay focused” (EUCLID 2019, 14) is similar in content to “organize your ideas” (EUCLID 2019, 2) under chapter one. Also, information under “Write clearly” (EUCLID 2019, 14,15) is similar to that under chapter one’s “essay paragraphs” (EUCLID 2019, 3). The part of chapter three that talks about plagiarism can be harmonized with information in chapter two.

From chapter three, I noticed some errors such that only the title was in the table of content and other subheadings were missing. The information from chapter three can be summarized and fitted into the content of chapter one, that is under “the essay” (EUCLID 2019, 1). In the EUCLID (2019) ACA-401D coursepack, “Do not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) sweeping such generalities as” (14) does not make sense and after sweeping, the word statement is missing. Other errors are numerically spelt as words and Arabic numerals. The words “connecting tissue” in this sentence “make sure to include a sentence or two of connective tissue” (EUCLID 2019, 15) are wrong. This might be error from accepting spelling and grammar check suggestions without checking it. On page 8, wrong bullet style and one word was bold “your” (EUCLID 2019). “Using many, many together for emphasis and use of informal writing style like “I ‘ve always” (EUCLID 2019, 19) is wrong

d) Fourth point explained

Chapter four started with eleven (11) important reminders (EUCLID 2019, 17) which focus on the use of punctuation, comma as well as active versus passive words. The next subheading focuses on the use of apostrophe before and after 's' and shows possessive singular noun and possessive plural noun, also when and how to use your, you 're, its', it's, that and which (EUCLID 2019, 18-19), and I versus me, the proper use of comma and the difference between exclusion and inclusion of comma in a sentence (EUCLID 2019, 20 – 22) . Inclusion of comma reduces ambiguity and will likely increase the effectiveness of the sentence. Another subheading explains, when a number should be written out, and when a numeral should be used? (EUCLID 2019, 21). The title should be grammar guide (ibid.). The table of content showed the subheadings.

Errors in chapter four are: the title of chapter four is literature review, however the entire content is different, and the explanation focused on different grammatical words and how to use them properly. One of the titled subheadings contradicts its' contents (EUCLID 2019, 21). The explanation started on how to write numbers. However, the latter deviated to the use of a, an, well, good. The lower paragraph should be another subheading. The subheadings are not numbered like chapter one.

e) Fifth point explained

Chapter five, is titled “**What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One?**,” the style guide is required to ensure that as a student of EUCLID, I will comply to the Turabian (Chicago style) so that my paper and final finished publications will be coherent and consistent with that of other students. I believe this style guide will enhance my writing skill and make my future publications compliant with international standards, especially when it is Turabian. The style guide provides instructions that I need to follow when writing my paper; the guides covers correct grammar, punctuation, vocabulary, preferred font size, sentence and paragraph length and paragraph numbering and indentation, it also covers the use of heading, how to write numbers, and so many other details. The level of compliance to the detailed specification in a guide depends on the type of writer. But this limits creativity and will make writing rigorous for creative writers. This means that organizations like BBC have a style guide for writing their news publications, using UK English. Under this chapter **the American vs. British English Basic Differences and Influences of Change** should be discussed (EUCLID 2019, 27). Since the use of US and UK English is an integral part of the style. I observed that the style of writing used in chapter five is good and the bullets were used properly (EUCLID 2019, 24 – 25).

The chapter will fail plagiarism test because there are no references added even where source is mentioned, the information provided is not complete.

3) CONCLUSION

I have written reports, meeting notes, success stories and technical brief. However, the materials for this ACA-401D period one has enhanced my academic and professional essay/paper writing skills. The coursepack is loaded with valuable information and instructions that aided in the writing of this response paper. I noticed different errors in each chapter of the coursepack such as the faulty/ improper use of chapter heading style, chapter title, sub-heading, sub-heading style, bullets, punctuation, quotation, upper and lower cases, grammatical errors, numbers, different citation styles and citation, different rule of style, three country's English (Australia , UK and US), different abbreviation to represent one word/phase, overcrowded page amongst others. Thus, I can conclude that the writing of ACA-401D lacked coherency and consistency, as required for all papers. I believe that as I navigate through the periods of this course, I will perfect the use of Zotero and Turabian style, CMS crib sheet as well as EUCLID templates.

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